

*EUROPEAN CENTRE FOR
MEDIUM-RANGE WEATHER FORECASTS*

*THE DESCRIPTION OF THE
ECMWF/WMO GLOBAL OBSERVATIONAL DATA SET*

1991

ADDENDUM

ECMWF/WMO GLOBAL OBSERVATIONAL DATA SET

Since the beginning of 1990 the data extraction service for the ECMWF/WMO Observational data set has been withdrawn. However, a tape copying service is still available.

This means that the magnetic tape output is restricted to internal bit format, and that printed output is no longer available. Also, the data are only available globally, for all parameters, at all reporting times.

The period covered is from 1 January 1980 to 31 December 1989 inclusive. It is not anticipated that any further data will be added to the data sets.

Each 6250 bpi magnetic tape contains 6 months of observational data starting 1 January or 1 July.

Each 1600 bpi magnetic tape contains 2 months of observational data starting 1 January, 1 March, 1 May, 1 July, 1 September or 1 November.

The standard charge for each magnetic tape copy required for data up to 31 December 1984 will be £55, and for data after 1 January 1985 the standard charge will be £80 per tape copy.

THE ECMWF/WMO GLOBAL OBSERVATIONAL DATA SET

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Part I: Description of the Data Set

This includes copies of raw observational surface data received via the WMO GTS and extracted from surface reports in the ECMWF database for the main synoptic hours 00, 06, 12 and 18 UT. Stations have been selected on the basis of frequency of receipt at ECMWF during the period. No ship observations other than ocean weather ships have been included.

1. Period covered from 1 January 1980 to 31 December 1988 inclusive.
2. The data set includes surface reports for the reporting times 00, 06, 12 and 18 UT from a selection of land stations on the WMO master list and a number of ocean weather ships. The selection has been based mainly on stations and ships received at ECMWF on 75% of occasions for three representative months (April and October 1982, and July 1983).
3. From the surface reports, the following parameters have been extracted and archived: temperature, dew point, mean sea level pressure, precipitation amount, low level cloud amount, cloud information (C_1 , C_m , C_h), maximum temperature or minimum temperature, ground temperature, state of ground, and pressure tendency.
4. A station list is written at the beginning of each magnetic tape, and internally reports are given in the order on the list. Missing value indicators are stored as necessary to maintain a constant internal record layout. The detailed format is given in Part III.
5. Magnetic tape output format options for reports can be selected as follows:
 - FGGE IIB format
 - The internal bit storage format together with unpacking software written in FORTRAN (see Part III).

Data will be made available on unlabelled nine track, odd parity magnetic tape written at 1600 or 6250 bpi. Examples of the numbers of tapes needed are given in Part IV.

6. Printed output format may be requested. Observations will be listed in tabular form. 50 observations may be accommodated on one page of printed output.

7. STATION LIST:

01001	01006	01008	01010	01023	01025	01028	01033	01035	01043
01047	01049	01053	01055	01059	01061	01062	01065	01067	01075
01078	01089	01098	01102	01106	01115	01121	01131	01149	01152
01160	01199	01205	01210	01212	01215	01218	01228	01241	01262
01271	01288	01306	01311	01316	01317	01321	01325	01328	01351
01366	01371	01372	01374	01379	01384	01389	01403	01406	01412
01415	01424	01427	01436	01439	01442	01445	01448	01465	01467
01476	01477	01478	01481	01482	01484	01488	01494	01498	
02012	02020	02032	02044	02048	02060	02086	02096	02104	02108
02112	02120	02124	02128	02142	02144	02156	02186	02196	02200
02206	02222	02226	02232	02234	02248	02254	02259	02262	02286
02288	02296	02304	02306	02310	02316	02324	02336	02342	02366
02376	02400	02404	02406	02410	02412	02418	02428	02444	02446
02458	02460	02464	02474	02496	02512	02520	02524	02526	02530
02544	02550	02555	02556	02562	02564	02566	02570	02576	02582
02584	02586	02588	02590	02592	02606	02607	02616	02622	02624
02626	02630	02636	02638	02640	02650	02654	02664	02666	02672
02680	02801	02805	02807	02823	02836	02844	02845	02848	02864
02867	02869	02874	02875	02879	02897	02901	02903	02905	02910
02911	02913	02915	02917	02919	02921	02924	02929	02935	02942
02944	02945	02949	02952	02958	02961	02963	02965	02966	02970
02972	02974	02976	02980	02981	02982	02984	02986		
03005	03017	03022	03026	03066	03068	03075	03091	03093	03100
03106	03135	03140	03160	03162	03171	03177	03185	03204	03222
03240	03257	03262	03302	03318	03334	03360	03377	03396	03414
03496	03502	03534	03558	03586	03590	03603	03672	03715	03740
03746	03772	03776	03797	03804	03817	03827	03839	03853	03855
03862	03884	03894	03917	03952	03953	03955	03957	03960	03962
03964	03965	03969	03970	03971	03974	03976	03980		
04004	04005	04013	04014	04018	04023	04030	04038	04045	04048
04053	04056	04063	04064	04065	04073	04077	04082	04085	04089
04097	04202	04220	04230	04231	04250	04260	04261	04270	04272
04350	04360	04381	04390						
06009	06011	06030	06041	06052	06060	06070	06071	06087	06089
06104	06110	06119	06120	06147	06151	06179	06180	06191	06193
06210	06225	06235	06240	06250	06260	06265	06268	06270	06275
06280	06290	06300	06310	06320	06325	06330	06344	06350	06370
06375	06380	06400	06407	06408	06431	06432	06447	06449	06450
06451	06456	06458	06470	06476	06478	06479	06481	06490	06590
06610	06612	06643	06660	06670	06672	06680	06700	06702	06720
06724	06730	06750	06753	06759	06760	06762	06770	06782	06786
06791	06792	06794	06990						
07002	07005	07010	07015	07017	07024	07027	07037	07038	07061
07070	07100	07110	07119	07121	07130	07139	07143	07147	07149
07150	07157	07168	07169	07172	07179	07180	07181	07186	07190
07197	07200	07207	07222	07230	07240	07249	07257	07265	07270
07280	07283	07288	07292	07295	07299	07314	07315	07335	07354
07382	07385	07412	07434	07442	07460	07470	07477	07481	07486
07497	07502	07510	07524	07535	07549	07558	07577	07579	07587
07588	07591	07602	07607	07610	07621	07627	07630	07635	07643
07646	07647	07650	07660	07667	07690	07720	07747	07756	07761
07765	07780	07785	07790						
08001	08008	08015	08023	08027	08045	08055	08075	08141	08160
08181	08202	08221	08238	08280	08284	08306	08314	08348	08360
08373	08391	08410	08419	08433	08451	08482	08487	08495	08501
08505	08509	08512	08515	08521	08524	08530	08536	08538	08543
08545	08549	08554	08557	08562	08566	08568	08571	08575	08594

09091 09161 09162 09170 09177 09184 09193 09249 09261 09264
09280 09359 09361 09379 09385 09393 09449 09453 09454 09460
09469 09474 09479 09488 09490 09492 09499 09548 09552 09554
09558 09567 09569 09577 09578 09582

10002 10005 10006 10007 10015 10020 10026 10034 10035 10113
10122 10126 10129 10131 10147 10156 10203 10215 10218 10224
10235 10253 10305 10313 10314 10317 10325 10338 10348 10381
10382 10384 10400 10406 10410 10427 10430 10438 10444 10452
10501 10510 10513 10515 10526 10532 10542 10544 10609 10615
10635 10637 10639 10655 10658 10671 10675 10685 10688 10704
10706 10708 10723 10727 10729 10737 10738 10742 10761 10763
10776 10791 10803 10815 10818 10836 10838 10852 10866 10875
10893 10900 10908 10929 10946 10948 10961 10962 10963 10980

11010 11022 11028 11030 11035 11036 11101 11105 11112 11120
11128 11130 11143 11146 11150 11155 11157 11165 11190 11204
11212 11231 11240 11406 11414 11438 11448 11457 11464 11487
11502 11518 11520 11541 11603 11636 11648 11659 11679 11683
11698 11710 11723 11735 11750 11766 11774 11782 11787 11816
11826 11841 11858 11903 11916 11930 11934 11968

12100 12105 12115 12120 12125 12135 12150 12160 12185 12195
12200 12205 12210 12215 12230 12235 12240 12250 12270 12272
12280 12285 12295 12300 12310 12330 12345 12360 12375 12385
12399 12400 12415 12418 12424 12435 12455 12465 12469 12485
12488 12490 12495 12497 12500 12510 12520 12530 12540 12550
12560 12566 12570 12575 12580 12585 12595 12600 12625 12650
12660 12690 12695 12772 12805 12812 12822 12825 12838 12843
12851 12860 12882 12892 12910 12915 12920 12925 12935 12942
12960 12970 12982 12992

13014 13026 13067 13105 13116 13131 13150 13157 13183 13209
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13363 13376 13388 13452 13462 13473 13493 13562 13583 13586
13592 13600 13615 13622 13624 13629

15004 15010 15020 15052 15063 15080 15085 15090 15108 15111
15120 15145 15150 15170 15197 15200 15209 15230 15235 15247
15260 15261 15280 15292 15296 15302 15310 15335 15338 15340
15346 15350 15360 15375 15377 15405 15409 15410 15420 15444
15450 15460 15470 15480 15482 15490 15491 15499 15511 15526
15535 15544 15552 15614 15615 15625 15627 15640 15655 15712
15730

16008 16020 16021 16033 16040 16045 16059 16061 16066 16072
16076 16080 16084 16090 16094 16095 16105 16108 16110 16115
16116 16120 16124 16134 16149 16153 16158 16170 16179 16191
16206 16219 16230 16242 16243 16252 16261 16270 16280 16289
16300 16310 16320 16325 16350 16360 16362 16400 16405 16420
16429 16453 16460 16470 16480 16490 16520 16529 16560 16597
16614 16622 16627 16641 16643 16648 16667 16675 16682 16710
16716 16723 16732 16734 16738 16743 16746 16749 16754

17022 17026 17030 17038 17050 17056 17060 17067 17082 17090
17092 17096 17112 17115 17116 17124 17128 17129 17150 17170
17180 17184 17190 17195 17200 17202 17218 17240 17244 17280
17292 17300 17350 17600 17601 17609

20046 20069 20087 20107 20274 20292 20353 20357 20667 20674
20744 20891

21358	21432	21504	21647	21824	21931	21946	21965	21982	
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22408	22422	22438	22471	22522	22550	22583	22602	22621	22641
22657	22676	22721	22768	22778	22802	22820	22837	22845	22854
22887	22892	22954							
23022	23032	23074	23105	23146	23205	23219	23226	23256	23274
23330	23383	23405	23412	23418	23472	23552	23606	23631	23678
23701	23711	23724	23734	23803	23804	23849	23884	23891	23914
23921	23933	23955	23966						
24105	24125	24143	24266	24329	24343	24507	24561	24629	24641
24671	24688	24738	24817	24908	24944	24959	24966		
25123	25173	25248	25399	25400	25551	25563	25594	25621	25677
25703	25821	25913	25954	25956					
26038	26059	26063	26078	26094	26115	26167	26231	26242	26247
26258	26298	26313	26348	26378	26406	26422	26477	26498	26509
26524	26544	26554	26535	26629	26645	26659	26666	26695	26702
26730	26763	26781	26825	26832	26850	26863	26882	26887	26898
26941	26951	26961	26997						
27037	27051	27066	27083	27113	27196	27217	27225	27242	27271
27329	27355	27373	27393	27402	27479	27532	27553	27595	27612
27648	27665	27679	27703	27707	27731	27823	27857	27906	27928
27947	27962								
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28661	28679	28698	28711	28722	28748	28838	28879	28900	28909
28952									
29231	29263	29282	29313	29356	29574	29612	29634	29698	29807
29838	29865								
30054	30230	30309	30372	30393	30433	30521	30554	30635	30673
30692	30710	30758	30802	30823	30879	30935	30949	30965	
31004	31088	31137	31168	31300	31329	31369	31416	31484	31510
31538	31707	31735	31829	31873	31909	31960			
32053	32061	32098	32150	32165	32186	32217	32389	32411	32540
32564	32618								
33008	33019	33027	33036	33041	33135	33177	33261	33275	33301
33317	33325	33345	33377	33393	33415	33429	33466	33506	33526
33562	33587	33631	33658	33663	33711	33777	33791	33815	33837
33869	33889	33902	33910	33924	33946	33983	33990		
34009	34122	34152	34172	34186	34240	34247	34300	34336	34357
34363	34391	34415	34504	34519	34523	34545	34560	34579	34601
34655	34691	34712	34731	34747	34759	34824	34838	34858	34866
34880	34929								
35078	35108	35121	35133	35188	35229	35358	35361	35394	35406
35416	35529	35576	35671	35700	35746	35796	35925		
36003	36061	36177	36428	36498	36665	36729	36859	36870	36982
37018	37031	37054	37085	37171	37228	37235	37260	37395	37432
37472	37484	37549	37553	37575	37686	37709	37735	37789	37907
37985									

38001	38062	38081	38198	38232	38262	38341	38353	38388	38392
38413	38457	38507	38545	38613	38687	38696	38750	38763	38836
38880	38895	38927	38954	38974					
40007	40016	40022	40030	40039	40045	40061	40066	40072	40080
40083	40087	40100	40155	40165	40180	40184	40199	40250	40255
40260	40270	40310	40340	40356	40357	40361	40362	40372	40373
40375	40394	40400	40405	40416	40420	40427	40428	40430	40438
40439	40445	40448	40449	40452	40462	40468	40474	40476	40477
40480	40495	40498	40564	40568	40569	40570	40572	40575	40576
40597									
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41685	41710	41712	41715	41739	41744	41749	41756	41765	41768
41780	41855	41858	41915	41917	41941				
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42339	42348	42361	42369	42379	42398	42410	42415	42452	42475
42492	42559	42571	42591	42623	42634	42647	42667	42675	42701
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42895	42909	42934	42971	42977					
43003	43014	43041	43063	43086	43110	43117	43128	43149	43185
43189	43192	43198	43201	43213	43233	43237	43255	43279	43284
43295	43314	43321	43329	43333	43344	43353	43369	43371	43400
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44305	44314	44341	44347	44352	44354	44358	44373		
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47090	47101	47105	47108	47112	47115	47119	47129	47130	47131
47133	47135	47138	47140	47143	47146	47152	47156	47159	47162
47165	47168	47184	47189	47192	47401	47412	47420	47426	47582
47590	47600	47648	47662	47678	47740	47778	47807	47827	47843
47898	47909	47918	47936	47945	47971	47991			
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48080	48094	48096	48099	48107	48108	48110	48112	48300	48303
48327	48331	48353	48356	48375	48378	48381	48400	48407	48431
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48583	48601	48615	48620	48647	48657	48665	48698	48820	48826
48839	48845	48855	48870	48877	48900	48917	48930	48935	48940
50136	50353	50434	50468	50527	50548	50557	50564	50603	50632
50658	50727	50745	50756	50774	50788	50844	50854	50888	50915
50949	50953	50963	50968	50978	50983				
51053	51076	51087	51133	51156	51243	51288	51334	51379	51431
51463	51467	51495	51542	51573	51644	51656	51709	51711	51716
51730	51765	51777	51811	51818	51828	51848	51886		
52118	52203	52267	52323	52378	52418	52436	52495	52533	52602
52652	52681	52713	52737	52754	52787	52818	52836	52866	52889
52908	52957	52996							
53068	53083	53149	53192	53231	53276	53336	53352	53391	53463
53480	53487	53502	53513	53529	53543	53564	53588	53593	53614
53646	53673	53698	53705	53723	53764	53772	53787	53798	53845
53863	53898	53915	53923	53959	53975				

54012	54026	54027	54049	54094	54096	54102	54115	54135	54157
54161	54186	54208	54218	54226	54236	54259	54273	54292	54308
54311	54324	54337	54342	54374	54377	54386	54401	54405	54423
54436	54471	54483	54493	54497	54511	54527	54534	54539	54587
54602	54616	54656	54662	54714	54725	54753	54776	54808	54823
54826	54836	54843	54857	54863	54906	54916	54938	54945	
55228	55279	55299	55472	55578	55591	55664	55696	55773	
56004	56018	56021	56029	56033	56046	56065	56079	56080	56096
56106	56116	56137	56146	56172	56193	56247	56257	56294	56312
56374	56385	56444	56462	56492	56571	56651	56671	56691	56739
56751	56768	56778	56786	56838	56945	56951	56954	56964	56966
56969	56985								
57006	57016	57036	57046	57067	57073	57083	57127	57178	57193
57237	57245	57259	57265	57279	57290	57297	57306	57328	57348
57378	57399	57411	57426	57447	57461	57476	57494	57515	57554
57584	57598	57622	57633	57655	57662	57679	57707	57713	57745
57766	57776	57795	57799	57816	57832	57845	57853	57866	57902
57932	57957	57972	57993						
58027	58040	58102	58144	58150	58203	58208	58221	58238	58251
58265	58314	58321	58334	58345	58367	58424	58437	58445	58457
58472	58477	58506	58527	58556	58569	58606	58633	58646	58653
58659	58666	58715	58725	58726	58731	58754	58813	58834	58847
58849	58853	58911	58921	58927	58931	58944	58965	58968	58974
59007	59023	59046	59058	59072	59082	59087	59096	59102	59117
59134	59158	59209	59211	59254	59265	59278	59287	59293	59316
59345	59358	59362	59417	59431	59456	59493	59501	59559	59562
59567	59632	59644	59658	59663	59673	59758	59792	59838	59845
59855	59948	59981	59985						
60001	60005	60010	60015	60020	60030	60035	60040	60060	60096
60101	60105	60107	60115	60127	60135	60141	60150	60155	60156
60185	60191	60195	60210	60220	60230	60250	60265	60285	60318
60340	60355	60360	60390	60402	60419	60425	60430	60444	60445
60468	60475	60490	60518	60522	60525	60535	60545	60549	60550
60555	60559	60566	60571	60580	60581	60590	60602	60607	60611
60620	60630	60656	60670	60680	60710	60714	60715	60720	60725
60734	60735	60738	60740	60745	60748	60750	60760	60765	60769
60770	60775								
61024	61036	61043	61049	61052	61075	61080	61090	61091	61096
61099	61202	61214	61223	61226	61230	61233	61240	61250	61257
61265	61270	61272	61277	61285	61291	61293	61296	61297	61401
61403	61415	61421	61437	61442	61450	61461	61489	61497	61498
61499	61600	61612	61627	61630	61641	61666	61679	61687	61695
61698	61699	61701	61766	61820	61829	61832	61833	61856	61901
61902	61931	61967	61968	61970	61972	61974	61976	61980	61984
61986	61988	61990	61996	61997	61998				
62002	62007	62010	62016	62019	62053	62055	62056	62059	62063
62103	62120	62124	62131	62161	62176	62259	62271	62300	62306
62318	62333	62366	62387	62393	62405	62414	62417	62441	62462
62465	62600	62620	62640	62641	62650	62660	62680	62700	62730
62750	62751	62760	62762	62770	62771	62772	62795	62805	62840
62880	62941								

63021 63023 63125 63170 63235 63250 63260 63270 63331 63332
63333 63334 63340 63402 63403 63450 63451 63453 63460 63471
63473 63474 63478 63533 63612 63624 63641 63661 63671 63695
63708 63714 63717 63720 63723 63729 63733 63740 63756 63766
63789 63790 63791 63793 63799 63801 63816 63820 63832 63844
63862 63866 63870 63887 63894 63932 63962 63971 63980 63995

64387 64390 64400 64401 64402 64403 64405 64450 64452 64453
64454 64456 64459 64500 64501 64503 64507 64510 64550 64551
64552 64556 64560 64565 64600 64601 64605 64610 64650 64654
64655 64656 64658 64659 64660 64661 64662 64851 64860 64870
64882 64890 64893 64900 64910 64911 64912 64920 64931 64950
64960 64961 64971

65046 65306 65319 65330 65335 65338 65344 65351 65352 65357
65361 65376 65380 65387 65418 65467 65472 65501 65502 65503
65507 65510 65516 65522 65528 65536 65545 65548 65555 65557
65560 65562 65563 65578 65585 65592 65594 65599 65660

66104 66130 66160 66240 66270 66310 66318 66325 66390

67001 67004 67005 67009 67012 67023 67025 67027 67037 67045
67073 67083 67095 67113 67117 67137 67143 67157 67161 67194
67197 67205 67215 67217 67223 67237 67241 67243 67261 67273
67283 67285 67295 67297 67315 67323 67335 67341 67413 67441
67461 67475 67477 67489 67531 67541 67561 67581 67587 67633
67641 67663 67665 67673 67693 67743 67753 67765 67775 67843
67853 67861 67867 67885 67965 67969 67975 67977 67983 67991

68010 68014 68016 68018 68024 68026 68032 68054 68104 68110
68112 68116 68148 68174 68176 68180 68182 68184 68190 68212
68226 68242 68244 68252 68258 68262 68268 68276 68288 68296
68300 68312 68322 68332 68338 68342 68344 68350 68351 68352
68362 68368 68370 68372 68378 68380 68388 68396 68406 68408
68416 68424 68438 68442 68454 68461 68462 68478 68496 68512
68524 68528 68530 68536 68542 68546 68550 68564 68572 68574
68580 68584 68588 68614 68618 68624 68638 68648 68668 68674
68712 68718 68722 68728 68736 68738 68742 68754 68816 68818
68826 68828 68832 68842 68858 68902 68906 68916 68920 68926
68928 68938 68994

70026 70086 70133 70200 70231 70251 70261 70273 70308 70316
70326 70350 70361 70398 70454

71043 71051 71062 71066 71069 71072 71073 71076 71078 71079
71081 71082 71090 71091 71093 71094 71098 71104 71107 71109
71120 71123 71138 71140 71141 71143 71145 71187 71600 71601
71603 71604 71621 71624 71625 71627 71705 71707 71709 71711
71714 71717 71722 71725 71730 71731 71735 71749 71803 71805
71807 71811 71815 71816 71818 71819 71821 71822 71825 71826
71828 71831 71834 71836 71842 71846 71848 71852 71855 71862
71863 71867 71869 71870 71871 71872 71874 71877 71884 71888
71889 71891 71892 71893 71896 71899 71900 71905 71906 71907
71909 71912 71913 71915 71917 71919 71920 71922 71924 71925
71926 71927 71929 71932 71934 71935 71936 71938 71940 71944
71945 71946 71948 71951 71953 71957 71958 71964 71965 71966
71967

72201	72202	72203	72205	72206	72208	72211	72212	72217	72218
72219	72223	72226	72228	72231	72234	72235	72240	72242	72248
72250	72251	72253	72256	72259	72261	72262	72264	72265	72266
72267	72270	72274	72278	72280	72290	72295	72304	72306	72308
72310	72312	72317	72324	72326	72327	72330	72334	72340	72341
72344	72353	72360	72363	72365	72370	72386	72389	72390	72401
72405	72406	72407	72408	72411	72414	72422	72423	72428	72429
72432	72434	72438	72440	72445	72446	72450	72451	72456	72460
72464	72465	72469	72476	72486	72487	72488	72494	72503	72508
72509	72515	72518	72519	72520	72524	72528	72530	72532	72533
72537	72540	72546	72561	72562	72564	72569	72572	72576	72578
72583	72597	72606	72608	72617	72618	72635	72645	72651	72654
72658	72661	72662	72665	72670	72677	72681	72683	72688	72693
72698	72712	72734	72741	72743	72745	72747	72753	72758	72764
72765	72767	72768	72773	72775	72785	72793	72797		

74486 74494

76122	76151	76160	76220	76225	76243	76342	76382	76405	76423
76458	76499	76525	76548	76556	76571	76577	76581	76612	76625
76632	76644	76648	76654	76665	76679	76680	76687	76689	76692
76695	76723	76737	76750	76762	76775	76805	76845	76848	76855

78016	78062	78073	78088	78092	78109	78121	78255	78313	78317
78325	78348	78349	78353	78360	78365	78367	78384	78388	78397
78457	78478	78482	78486	78526	78583	78615	78537	78641	78647
78650	78663	78730	78762	78806	78862	78894	78397	78907	78925
78946	78954	78970	78982	78988					

80001	80009	80022	80028	80035	80036	80044	80048	80063	80074
80077	80084	80089	80091	80094	80097	80099	80110	80132	80139
80144	80175	80210	80211	80214	80219	80222	80234	80241	80252
80259	80300	80308	80315	80322	80336	80337	80342	80346	80354
80361	80370	80372	80385	80398	80403	80405	80407	80410	80412
80413	80415	80416	80419	80421	80423	80425	80427	80428	80435
80438	80444	80447	80448	80450	80453	80457	80462		

81202 81209 81225 81250 81251 81253 81401 81405 81408 81415

82024	82098	82106	82113	82191	82198	82212	82240	82246	82280
82287	82331	82353	82392	82397	82400	82410	82418	82425	82533
82562	82564	82571	82578	82583	82586	82596	82610	82640	82668
82678	82704	82723	82765	82784	82807	82825	82861	82900	82915
82930	82975	82983	82986	82994					

83064	83096	83182	83208	83229	83236	83242	83264	83288	83309
83339	83344	83348	83358	83361	83377	83386	83393	83405	83437
83470	83483	83492	83498	83526	83552	83587	83592	83611	83618
83630	83648	83650	83687	83692	83698	83702	83719	83721	83722
83738	83743	83766	83781	83782	83836	83842	83844	83881	83887
83897	83907	83914	83927	83936	83948	83964	83967	83980	83995
83997									

84018	84071	84117	84203	84239	84265	84370	84377	84390	84401
84425	84435	84444	84452	84455	84472	84474	84501	84515	84531
84534	84542	84564	84628	84658	84673	84677	84686	84691	84721
84735	84752	84782							

85041	85043	85104	85114	85123	85141	85154	85196	85201	85207
85223	85230	85242	85245	85247	85268	85283	85289	85293	85315
85345	85364	85365	85406	85417	85442	85460	85469	85470	85486
85488	85543	85574	85585	85629	85682	85732	85743	85766	85799
85862	85874	85889	85930	85934	85967	85972			

86011	86017	86065	86097	86134	86135	86192	86218	86223	86233
86248	86255	86260	86296	86297	86330	86350	86360	86370	86430
86440	86450	86460	86490	86500	86530	86560	86565	86580	86585
86595									

87007	87016	87046	87047	87065	87078	87097	87129	87149	87155
87162	87178	87187	87211	87217	87222	87244	87257	87270	87289
87305	87311	87320	87322	87328	87344	87349	87374	87393	87395
87400	87405	87418	87436	87448	87453	87467	87480	87497	87506
87509	87532	87534	87544	87548	87574	87576	87596	87623	87645
87648	87663	87679	87688	87692	87715	87736	87750	87763	87765
87774	87784	87791	87803	87814	87828	87852	87860	87880	87896
87903	87909	87912	87925	87928	87934	87938			

88890	88903	88946	88952	88963	88968	88971			
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89001	89002	89022	89034	89045	89050	89052	89055	89060	89061
89062	89066	89132	89512	89532	89542	89544	89571	89592	89606
89611	89657	89664							

91066	91165	91182	91190	91217	91245	91275	91285	91334	91348
91353	91356	91366	91376	91378	91408	91413	91490	91507	91520
91527	91551	91554	91555	91558	91565	91568	91577	91582	91592
91601	91610	91629	91631	91636	91643	91648	91650	91652	91659
91660	91670	91680	91683	91691	91693	91697	91699	91753	91754
91762	91765	91772	91776	91780	91784	91792	91800	91804	91811
91822	91826	91830	91840	91843	91925	91930	91938	91941	91943
91944	91945	91948	91952	91954	91958				

93003	93011	93119	93199	93308	93401	93434	93516	93545	93614
93709	93780	93844	93896	93944	93997				

94295	94296	94298	94386	94986					
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95502

96009	96011	96035	96073	96091	96109	96145	96163	96179	96195
96221	96237	96249	96253	96295	96315	96413	96421	96441	96449
96471	96491	96509	96645	96685	96743	96805	96933	96996	

97180	97230	97260	97300	97340	97372	97390	97560		
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98135	98223	98232	98325	98328	98329	98429	98431	98440	98444
98550	98618	98646	98748	98753	98755	98836			

4 ocean weather ships: C7C C7L C7M C7R

Part II: Requests for Data

In addition to providing the computer resources needed to set up these global data sets, ECMWF provides a service in extracting any reasonable subset of the data (including sub-areas) from the global data set.

The data and any necessary software will be supplied, if so required, on magnetic tape and a standard fee will be charged. This fee is considerably less for the period up to 31 December 1984 due to the support provided by WMO to extract the data set for that period. The number of tapes required will depend on the amount of data, the output format and the tape density. Some examples are given in Part IV. Alternatively or additionally, data will be prepared in the form of printed lists and a standard fee will be charged per 100 pages (or part thereof) of listings.

1. Requests for data should be made using the standard order forms, using one form for each separate request. An order form is included at the back of this brochure. All options are pre-defined, to be selected by marking the boxes on the form.
2. A user can define:
 - the output format
 - the time interval
 - the observation hours
 - reports selected by area, WMO block number, or WMO station number, where area subsets are based on regular rectangular areas with edges along latitude and longitude lines

It is not possible to select elements from within a report; the whole report will be returned.

3. For magnetic tape requests, data will be delivered on unlabelled odd parity, nine track magnetic tape written at 1600 or 6250 bpi. Each request will be delivered on a separate magnetic tape (or tapes).
4. For printed output requests, data will be delivered in the form of computer produced listings.
5. Separate request must be made for data up to 31 December 1984 and from 1 January 1985 onwards.
6. For data up and including 31 December 1984 the standard charge for each magnetic tape will be £50.

7. For data from 1 January 1985 to 31 December 1988 the charge for data on magnetic tape will be calculated using

$$\text{COST} = \alpha N + \alpha \gamma M$$

where α is the "unit cost" (currently £70)

γ is 0.05

M is the number of months or part months comprising the period for which data are requested.

N is the number of magnetic tapes to be written.

Users requesting data at 1600 bpi will be charged on the basis of what the cost would have been if 6250 bpi tape were used, plus an additional charge of 70 pounds sterling for each 1600 bpi tape required over and above the number of tapes that would have been required had 6250 bpi been used.

8. For printed output the standard charge is £20 for each 100 pages (or part thereof) of listings.
9. The above handling charges, which are payable to ECMWF, include postage by air mail, and will remain in force until 31 December 1989. Extracted tapes will be dispatched to users by air mail only - no arrangements will be entered into with third party carriers.

Discounts will be given for large orders as follows:

orders in excess of £ 1,500	-	10% of that part of the normal charge which exceeds £1,500
orders in excess of £ 5,000	-	£350, plus 20% of that part of the normal charge which exceeds £5000
orders in excess of £10,000	-	£1,350, plus 25% of that part of the normal charge which exceeds £10,000.

10. Charges may be paid in pounds sterling or US Dollars; charges in US Dollars will be based on the charge computed in pounds sterling with an exchange rate applied of 1.75 US Dollars per pound; this exchange rate will be adjusted, if the rate of exchange differs by more than ± 0.25 US Dollars from 1.75 US Dollars per pound. The exchange rate at the time of invoicing will be used to interpret these rules if payment is requested in US Dollars.

11. Requests for data should be sent to:

The Director
ECMWF
Shinfield Park
Reading/Berkshire
RG2 9AX
UNITED KINGDOM

Part III: Description of the Internal Format for Observational Data Set

The very first block contains a station list; the following blocks contain observational data. One data block comprises identification data (year, month, day and hour) and the meteorological parameters of K stations in the order of the station list.

Station list				
K	WMO no.1	WMO no.2	...	WMO no.K

Data part				
YYMDDTT1	station 1,1	station 1,2	...	station 1,K

YYMDDTT2	station 2,1	station 2,2	...	station 2,K
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...

STATION LIST

Parameter	Number of bits	Remarks
K	13	Number of stations
WMO no.	30	WMO number of land station/ocean weather ship

DATA PART

Parameter	Number of bits	Remarks
YEAR	7	00...99
MONTH	4	01...12
DAY	5	01...31
HOUR	5	observation time 00, 06, 12, 18 GMT
CODE	5	type of station (11=SYNOP, 14=Automated SYNOP 21=ocean weather ship)
SIGNH	1	sign of the station altitude
ALTITUDE	13	station altitude (m)
SIGN1	1	0 = LATIT positive, 1 = LATIT negative
LATIT	14	station latitude, e.g. -56.77 is represented by 5677
SIGN2	1	0 = LONGIT positive, 1 = LONGIT negative
LONGIT	15	station longitude, e.g. 135.62 is represented by 13562
T(+999)	11	temperature (0.1°C)
Td(+999)	11	Dew point (0.1°C)
INDPZ	4	indicates whether PZ is pressure or height (see Table A)
PZ(+2000)	14	pressure/geopotential height (0.1 hPa/m)
RRtp	5	time-period indicator for precipitation (hours)
RR	14	precipitation (0.1 mm)

DD	6	wind direction (tens of degree), variable=62
FF	7	wind speed (m/s)
W	7	past weather (0...9, 00...99)
WW	7	present weather (00...99)
N	4	total cloud amount (OCTAS)
Nh	4	amount of lowest clouds (OCTAS)
Txp	5	time-period indicator for maximum temperature (hours)
Tx(+999)	11	maximum temperature (0.1°C)
Tnp	5	time-period indicator for minimum temperature (hours)
Tn(+999)	11	minimum temperature (0.1°C)
Tg(+999)	11	ground temperature (0.1°C)
E	4	state of ground (0...9)
ap	2	time-period indicator for pressure tendency (0=3 hours, 1=24 hours, 3=missing)
ac	4	pressure characteristic (WMO Code=0200)
a	10	pressure tendency (0.1 hPa)
Cl	4	low clouds (0...9)
Cm	4	medium clouds (0...9)
Ch	4	high clouds (0...9)
240 = 21 (date) + 219 (parameters)		

Each station always comprises 219 bits. Missing values are represented by the maximum possible value assigned to the appropriate bit field.

Table A: Table of pressure code

Value	Meaning
0	sea level
1	station level pressure
2	850 hPa geopotential
3	700 hPa geopotential
4	500 gpm pressure
5	1000 gpm pressure
6	2000 gpm pressure
7	3000 gpm pressure
8	4000 gpm pressure
9	900 hPa geopotential
10	1000 hPa geopotential
11	500 hPa geopotential

ORDER FORM FOR THE ECMWF/WMO OBSERVATIONAL DATA SET

NAME:

ORGANISATION:

ADDRESS:

TELEX/TELEPHONE NUMBER:

Tick and fill in the appropriate boxes below:

OUTPUT FORMAT:

on tape Internal bit format

TAPE DENSITY: (select one option)

1600 bpi Phase Encoded

6250 bpi

Tapes will be odd parity and nine tracks, with no labels.

Starting date (YYMMDD):

Ending date (YYMMDD):

OBSERVATION HOURS: 00 UT

06 UT

12 UT

18 UT

Data for the whole globe

Note: For data in internal bit format the unpacking software, in FORTRAN, will be written at the end of each tape in ASCII characters.

Invoice in US-Dollars requested

Data is supplied by ECMWF subject to the following conditions:

1. The supplied data will not be transmitted in whole or in part to any third party without the authorisation of ECMWF.
2. Articles, papers, or written scientific works of any form, based in whole or in part on data supplied by ECMWF, will contain an acknowledgement concerning the supplied data.
3. Access to the data is restricted to the scientists within the organisation of the data recipient working on the same computer installation.
4. The recipient of the data will accept responsibility for informing all data users of these conditions.

This is to certify that I/we agree to the above conditions with respect to the supply of data by ECMWF.

Signed:

Date:

=====

(For ECMWF internal use only)

Date of order received

Number of tapes

Number of printed pages

Amount charged for tapes

Amount charged for listings

Total amount charged

Invoice/Revenue Order No.

Budget Reference

Revenue of:

a. Authorised

Department Head

Date

b. Approved

Financial Comptroller

Date